

CURRENT ISSUES OF SOCIAL GERONTOLOGY

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Abstract. *This article discusses the current issues of social gerontology. In particular, today, globalized loneliness and an increase in the proportion of elderly people in the population are observed in all countries. In this regard, opinions were given about the UN population studies and the activities of providing medical and social assistance to the elderly and lonely elderly in our country.*

Keywords: *introvert, extrovert, types of communication in solitude, suffering from loneliness, aging factors, average life expectancy, demographic situation, increasing aging, medical and social care.*

Today, among the globalized problems, the problem of the increasing number of lonely elderly people in the population has been added. According to the data, "the aging process was 6.8% in the world in 2016, and now this indicator is 9.6%. According to the results of UN population studies, in 2050, the number of elderly people in the world may make up 22% of the world's population.

If we pay attention to the study of the concept of "loneliness" among young and old people and among the population of different ages and its social consequences, we can be sure that there are many problems in this regard. It is known that until today the concept of "loneliness" has been viewed as a social psychological phenomenon. Again, this is related to the emotional state of a person. In this case, two different cases can be seen: firstly, the positive case, and secondly, the negative case. The second situation is common in life. Many people do not want to admit that they are becoming lonely by being attached to social media.

Some people feel lonely despite having loved ones in society. Such people can be divided into introvert and extrovert categories. Introverts are people who want to live with their inner world and therefore seek solitude. Extroverts are people who are always among people and strive for communication. People of this category are active practitioners in life, who have the ability to quickly communicate with people of different categories during their interactions with everyone. They are considered to have the ability to communicate with everyone, although not very deeply, in any situation, and they often try to overcome loneliness by renewing their social circles. For introverts, being around people they respect and like can help overcome loneliness by turning to them. But there are no pure introverts and extroverts among the young or the old. There is a certain proportion here - it is natural that almost all people have suffered from loneliness at least once in their life. Another important aspect of the issue is that despite the large population in large cities in all countries, many people, especially the elderly, feel lonely. Big cities do not bring people together, today they serve to separate them. In this context, is loneliness a problem of today's society or is it an inseparable and inevitable part of the life given to each of us? This question is simply difficult to answer. For example: from the first days of birth, a person lives feeling the care of his mother and those around him. Loneliness is alien to him. As he begins to grow up, he compares himself to others by forming his "I", and his character is formed by forming his system of relationships. At the same time, feelings of loneliness appear in him. Sometimes teenagers are

afraid of being alone. The reason is that when they are alone, they start thinking about their life, their mistakes and achievements, and their future plans. It can also be a case of reluctance to acknowledge feelings of responsibility and accountability in a sense. Individuals who have lived a constant active life throughout their lives, who are public, who are in constant attention and recognition, perceive loneliness as a tragedy. The fact that most of this category of elderly people spend more time sitting in front of the TV, trying to spend their time in different circles, does not serve them to increase their knowledge and experience, to improve as a person, on the contrary, after spending such time, their problems become worse. Socrates wrote about this situation: "...there is no use for such people to escape from loneliness and go on trips, they take their problems there with them, no matter how sad they are". What type of communication can overcome loneliness? In this situation, such a type of communication is necessary, which should serve to give something to others, to the society, and not to get something. Loneliness may not be felt by a person during his work activity, during intense relationships with people. But most people feel lonely when they are alone at home. In such situations, it is also important to understand that being alone may not always be safe. Sometimes leaving a person alone with himself allows him to understand his own problems. But being alone for a long time and losing communication with others can cause psychological and somatic problems. Therefore, suffering from loneliness is an aspect that leads to a lack of new information and ideas.

Today, not all societies are struggling with the problem of loneliness among the elderly. By effectively organizing time in youth, a person can improve his knowledge, skills and abilities. Older people do not have all the opportunities that young people have. For this reason, in solving the problem of loneliness of the elderly, it is necessary to organize such places for the lonely elderly, so that in such social centers the elderly do not feel alone, they can share their knowledge and skills in which people of different ages communicate together, and teach young people from their life experiences. Young people do not always pay attention to the elderly because they are busy with their personal work. The situation is different for the elderly. It is natural for the elderly to lose many of their capabilities as they age. For example, not being able to see their favorite friends for a long time, the death of many of such friends, various diseases and other reasons can destroy them. Loneliness, as a social and cultural evil that is increasing in modern societies, is attracting the attention of many people in the world today. Classical sociologists such as E.Durkheim, M.Beber, E.Morena, L.Birta, G.Zimmel and E.Klianenberg, in their research, the reasons for people's pursuit of loneliness or the phenomenon of falling into loneliness were scientifically and theoretically analyzed on the example of urban life, and it is studied how the society of origin affects the relationships between people in life.

Today, another type of loneliness has been formed - the concept of social loneliness. If we try to analyze the state of loneliness in modern societies, which is caused by being attached to social networks in family relationships, business, we can be sure that social loneliness is usually perceived by most people as a negative state, which is caused by the lack of communication, lack of emotions and feelings. "Loneliness" is a term that has spread as quickly and widely as the word "globalization" today. Along with rapid development, urban population density is increasing, and loneliness among people is increasing. "Loneliness" is spreading widely in the social, spiritual and cultural life of the society as an urgent problem. At one time, during the Soviet era, social loneliness in the life of the society and the problems related to it were hardly studied in our country. Even the existence of this condition is denied. "Loneliness" was assessed as a condition not typical

of a society. The economic, political, and spiritual crisis of the same period intensified the state of social isolation. Along with the formation of modern societies, the problem of "social loneliness" grew and intensified in the life of the society. It affects the stability of society as a "globalized" problem today. It is possible to observe the following relations regarding the study of the phenomenon of this process: I. Yalom, K. Moustakas studied this problem in existential psychology. According to them, loneliness is actually something that has been in human nature since time immemorial. According to them, each person is unique and difficult for others to understand. They try to reason that their loneliness is because they are not understood by others. According to existentialists, "social loneliness" is not related to human pathology, but to his household and economic situation. Scientists such as L. Zilburg, K. Moustakas expressed their scientific views within the psychoanalytical approach to the problem of "social loneliness" within the framework of the neo-Freudian paradigm. It is necessary to study this problem from a sociological point of view, because in fact the concept of social loneliness is related to political, economic and social changes in the life of society. Sometimes it is caused by positive changes in this direction. For example, social isolation can be a transformation in tradition. There may be changes in the issues of collectivism and individualism in interpersonal relations. Sometimes, due to the separation of some individuals, whole social groups cannot get used to a new way of life, cannot get used to the real situation, and fall into social isolation. Social loneliness is a multifactorial problem in all societies today.

Population aging is a characteristic demographic situation in the countries of the world today. Over the past forty years, the number of retired people in our countries has increased. This leads to a decrease in the percentage of working people among the population. The increase in the number of elderly among the country's population leads to a decrease in the number of working-age among the youth. In fact, the demographic situation in the post-Soviet republics began to change in 1989. The fastest growing category of the elderly population was observed to increase due to 60-69-year olds and 80 years old and older. Another feature is that in the post-Soviet countries, which are located in the European part of the CIS countries, which we know as near abroad countries, while the average life expectancy of people is decreasing, the number of elderly people aged 60 and older among the population is increasing. In 2015, one out of every three residents of this region were 75 years old or older. The increase in the average life expectancy in recent years has raised the social problems related to old age and especially lonely old age among the urgent problems worldwide. In the increase of life expectancy, first of all, the achievements in the field of medicine during the last quarter of a century have an important place. In addition, in this regard, the improvement of human living conditions and the increase in well-being can be a special factor. Therefore, many researchers are interested in studying the physiological, pathological, psychological and social aspects of the life of the elderly in various fields of science, with the expected goal of determining the factors of longevity. The demographic situation determines the strategy of medical institutions to serve the population. In many countries today, the aging of the population and the increase in costs in the social and medical sectors associated with this process also creates the task of solving the problems. Over the past decades, many options have been proposed in this regard. In particular, in 1980, the UN proposed to set 60 years as the threshold for transitioning to old age. In fact, in 1963, 60-74 years old was accepted as the old age in the classification presented by the World Health Organization in the United Nations Population Program. In it, young seniors between 75-89 years, and over 90 years old are divided into the

category of long-lived people. To date, criteria for dividing the country into the category of underdeveloped and old countries based on the population of the country have also been developed. It was shown that, firstly, 4% of the country's population is 65 years and older, and secondly, 7% and older are elderly.

The aging of the world's population is alarming. Studying the problems of the elderly, especially the lonely elderly, and providing them with social support is becoming one of the hot topics. Among those who carried out effective research in this direction, when viewed on a global scale, foreign scientists such as J. Campbell, M. Heinsler, F. Khamdaran, S. Rishpon, S. Payne, M. Cheilhorn can be listed. Among them, Russian scientists L.F. Gulo, I.I. Vorobeva, B.C. Preobrazhensky, G.A. Ponomareva, L. Dvoretzky, L.A. Mylnikova and others can be listed. In their research, the causes of aging related to medicine, the social consequences of the increase in the proportion of elderly people in the population, and the issues of improving the effectiveness of medical and social services for lonely elderly people were studied in their research. But until now, this direction has not been fully and widely studied both abroad and in our country. A comprehensive approach to this direction is necessary, and the expected result will be the development of various categories in the field of social gerontology, and they will serve to increase the efficiency of providing social and medical services to the elderly population, and especially to the lonely elderly, to contribute to the increase in the life expectancy of the elderly population and the further improvement of their living conditions. In our opinion, research on this topic serves to show the importance and ways of applying the medical and social components of care for lonely elderly people. Also, conducting research in this regard should be directed to the following scientific tasks:

- interdisciplinary study of the problems of the elderly and lonely population;
- medical and social possibilities of gerontology and geriatrics explanation of the state of limitation;
- to study the effect of medicalization of human life on lonely elderly people;
- clarifying the direction of social activity;
- consumption of medical and social assistance by elderly people;
- social description of consumers of complex medical care at home;

It is important to carry out research on the provision of medical and social assistance to lonely elderly people and to justify the nature of this service, the relationship between medical and social components. The trend of population aging is accepted as a social law in technologically advanced countries. Conducting research in these directions allows studying political, economic, and cultural problems. This is primarily to support the creation of high-level living conditions for the elderly population. In this regard, while it is considered important to integrate the activities of all social institutions related to the activity in this direction, the health system is considered a leading factor. Because as a person grows older, his organism decreases its physiological properties. The medical component is the leading factor in providing care to the elderly. Therefore, providing social assistance to the elderly is not only social in nature, it is a medical-social activity. Naturally, this is based on the needs of social workers in the role distribution in this regard. But there is another aspect of the matter that needs to be remembered. In other words, in social work with the elderly, it is impossible to excessively medicalize their diseases and hypertrophy their socialization. For this, based on the principle of interdisciplinary communication, it is necessary to take into account the scientific and theoretical aspects of conducting research in the fields of

gerontology, geriatrics, and gerentosociology. At the same time, conducting research in this field requires optimization of the method of providing assistance to lonely elderly people in the system of multidisciplinary components existing in the field of gerentosociology. In the current situation, the scientific literature in this direction is insufficient. Therefore, it is necessary to use scientific literature published on medical sociology and gerentosociology. In our opinion, it is not about the creation of a third science, but about the intersection of the theory of medical and social work with the lonely elderly, and the medical methodology, which has an undoubted heuristic value. Medicalization is a positive process. Its main goal is to strengthen people's health. However, its excessive use can cause negative consequences. Providing medical care to the elderly alone should not become a promotion of self-medication and distribution of over-the-counter drugs. It is also wrong to interpret medical-social care as purely "medical" or purely "social". This process is necessary only to determine the physiological state of the elderly. The results of public surveys conducted as part of the research on improving the effectiveness of social support for lonely elderly people reveal that the majority of the elderly believe that public institutions or social service workers should take care of them, not themselves. The elderly, especially the elderly alone, believe that medical care is more important to them than social care. This situation again indicates that the provision of medical care for the elderly is well developed compared to the provision of social care. According to social service workers, the elderly is grateful that the social and medical assistance provided to them is organized in their own homes. Most of the elderly rate the quality of medical services higher than the quality of social services. At the same time, it is necessary to organize activities based on the principles of gender equality in the organization of this service. Most single seniors prefer inpatient care. At the same time, they want economic problems to be solved in this direction. But inpatient treatment has a significant impact on the quality of medical care.

In our opinion, it is more effective to conduct research in the field of social and medical assistance to lonely elderly people based on the functional model proposed by Academician A.V. Reshetnikov. It is important to cooperate with disciplines such as general psychology, medical statistics, theory of social work sociology based on interdisciplinary integration. The theoretical and practical significance of the conducted research is that it serves to make the life of lonely elderly people more meaningful, and allows the development of gerontological programs for social work with lonely elderly people in the region. Also, the research conducted in this regard will help to eliminate the imbalances found in working with lonely elderly people, allowing to use it as a criterion for evaluating medicalization or hypertrophied socialization.

Humanity has entered the third millennium with a number of problems during its historical development, including the phenomenon of aging and loneliness, which are causing serious problems today. For example, in the period between the last century and the present, it was observed that in some countries of the world, the situation was the following. In Germany, France and Britain it was 30%. The Scandinavian countries are at the forefront of this issue, in 2019 it was 46% in Norway, where one in two of the population is single. In Italy, where family values are relatively strong among European countries, 33 out of every 100 families are single families. The same indicator was 33.6% in 2019 among the countries of the European Union. Loneliness has been growing significantly in recent years in economically underdeveloped countries. For example, 10% of families in Mexico are single-person families. 50 years ago, this figure was 4%. In Angola, this figure has also increased from 4% to 11%. In the Republic of South Africa, it grew

by 15-27%. Between 1960 and 2015, the number of people living alone in China increased by 15%, in Japan - by 35%, and in the Republic of South Korea - by 15-27%. In Australia, one in four people live alone. (Table 1)

The dynamics of the share of single-person households in different countries

The population of the earth increased from 808 million to 1.4 billion in 60 years. But even within this indicator, it was observed that the share of people living alone is significant. Such a demographic situation certainly has an impact on changes in the family structure. According to J. Chely, a scientist from the USA, in recent years, families in Germany, Japan, Finland, and Estonia are increasing at the expense of single people. This is twice as many as those who have a partner and children. In 2007, the average number of two-person families in EU countries was half of the national average. By 2020, this indicator increased by 7%, and the number of families of this type was 19.5%.

According to the results of the 2015 studies, Russia is also approaching this indicator. 31% of Russian families were made up of one-person families (Table 2).

(Table 3)

Loneliness has always been condemned in the mentality of all the nations of the world. In particular, if a hundred years ago loneliness was considered a family tragedy, it was actually associated with death, but today loneliness has become associated with an increase in the well-being of people's lives. "Loneliness is leading the way in demographic change," historian Kim Chell, a professor at Leicester University, found. In the following decades, economic growth is observed in all countries. This, in turn, has led to an increase in the level of well-being, creating a situation where a person can meet his own needs even by living alone. Our World in Data economist Esteban Ortiz learned about it. Today, the level of loneliness is increasing mainly in large industrialized cities. In 2018, Theresa May, who even introduced the position of minister for singles affairs in Britain and worked in this position, said that the problems related to single people, especially single elderly people, are urgent today. Considering that 35% of the population in Britain is over 65 years old and 10% are aged 30-49, we can be sure that the problem is really serious. In 2021, the position of Minister of Loneliness was also introduced in Japan. The reason for this is the increased isolation of the elderly during the pandemic. Singles make up 47% of the population in Denmark. In this regard, the situation in the USA is not encouraging. The number of 18-34-year-olds among the population increased 10 times between 1950 and 2017. In 2020, among 55-64-year-olds, men increased by 52%. 40.5% of humen over 65 years of age are men, and only 14% are women.

Sudden changes in the transformation of the family can also be considered as another factor that causes the situation of people to become lonely.

From the conducted studies, it was found that in the period from the 60s of the last century to 2015, single-person families grew in most countries: South Korea and Denmark – by 24%, France – by 18%, Italy and Canada – by 20%, Japan and Great Britain – by 15%, USA and Australia – by 13%, China increased by 10 times. (Table 4)

As our country, as one of the equal subjects of the international community, has gained its place in the international arena and is strengthening cooperation relations with a number of countries of the world in various spheres of public life, along with the flow of foreign invitations to our country, various ideas and ideological views, various forms of popular culture have entered our country. Among such ideas, it is dangerous to increase the influence of views that serve

destruction, such as the promotion of loneliness. Our people have learned to live in a collective way of life since time immemorial. It is well known that our nation is collective in essence. The ratio of compromise and consensus is also unique in Uzbek mentality.

Growth dynamics of single-person families

With the change of certain social-political environment, spiritual-cultural approaches to compromise in the life of society, compromise can turn into consensus or alienation. In the development of society, the state of consensus has always been more positive than the state of compromise. Because the concept of consensus refers to the unity of common interests. In addition, situations of loneliness and individuality are alien to the concepts of succession and spiritual harmony in the nature of our people. The priority direction of the reforms carried out in our country is human interests and rights, providing equal opportunities to all citizens, including pensioners, war and labor veterans, disabled and lonely elderly people who are not left out of the state's real support and attention. In our country, the legal basis and organizational mechanism of social protection of elderly people have been created. New approaches in this regard are proposed in the updated draft of the constitution of our country. In the Decree PD-4906 "On measures to further improve the activities of the fund "Nuroni" for social support of Uzbekistan's veterans" and PR-2753 "On additional measures to improve the mechanism of payment of salaries, pensions, allowances and scholarships", Resolution "On social protection of the disabled in the Republic of Uzbekistan" and the Labor Code, as well as a number of other laws and documents, it is instructed that paying attention to lonely elderly people and respecting them is considered as one of the priority directions of important activities in the social sphere. There are more than 3.9 million pensioners in Uzbekistan today. The increase in the number of elderly people in recent years is also related to the increase in life expectancy in our country. This situation can also be seen as a reflection of the increase in living well-being. In our country, the elderly make up 6.7% of the total population. This is the lowest indicator among the CIS countries. In Russia, 28% of the country's population, 26% in Belarus, and 29% in Ukraine are in the pension system. Help Age International's research in our country shows that by 2030, the number of elderly people will increase by 11.6 percent. In 2050, this indicator is expected to increase to 19.4 percent. In Uzbekistan, a number of tasks have been defined and are being implemented at the level of state

policy for the elderly to spend their old age peacefully and comfortably. But at the same time, there are a number of problems, the solution of which will serve to improve the life of elderly people and increase their life expectancy. Among such problems, the need to increase the amount of allowances for the elderly should be considered as one of the most urgent. At the same time, caring for lonely elderly people, providing them with medical services, expanding the quality and scope of social services, solving problems related to nursing homes are the most urgent tasks in this regard. In order to provide assistance to lonely elderly people, it is necessary to organize voluntary groups of "Volunteers" among young people to make them feel that they are not alone, to actively communicate with them, to conduct various activities, to strengthen the provision of assistance through various social programs, to study and use international experience. the goal is to make sure that single seniors don't feel isolated.

REFERENCES

1. Sh.M. Mirziyoev. From national revival to national rise. Uzbekistan, Tashkent, 2020
2. Sh.M. Mirziyoev. Raising the standard and quality of life of our people to a new level is our most important task. Uzbekistan, Tashkent, 2020
3. C.R. Mills. Sociological imagination. Moscow, 2019
4. E.V. Klimova. Social loneliness in modern society. St. Petersburg, 2022
5. M. Bekmurodov. Uzbek mentality. Tashkent, 2011.
6. Sh.M. Sodikova. Current issues of sociology. Renaissance, Science/ Publishing,
7. Sh.M. Sodikova. The role of the elderly in educating young people in the spirit of love and loyalty to the country. Tashkent, "Yangi Avlod" publication, 2016
8. Sh.M. Sodikova. Family education. - Tashkent, "Spirituality" publishing house, 2019.
9. L.Q. Eryigitova. The negative impact of family disputes on the development of society. Society and innovation journal, No. 2, 2022,
10. C.R. Mills. Sociological imagination. Moscow, 2019
11. E.V. Klimova. Social loneliness in modern society. St. Petersburg, 2022.
12. Society and innovation journal, No. 2, 2022,